

It is apparent that the present method, besides being highly sensitive, is very simple to carry out as no extraction and no multiplicity of solvents are required.

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Isonitrosothiocamphor as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for Rhodium(III)

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Manuscript received 7 March 1988, revised 26 October 1988,
accepted 20 July 1989

ISONITROSOTHIOCAMPHOR (INTC) has been reported as an analytical reagent for palladium¹, cobalt² and copper³. At room temperature rhodium(III) shows no colour reaction with the reagent but forms a red chelate with INTC while heating on a boiling water-bath. The complex is extractable into chloroform. Taking advantage of this phenomenon, a simple spectrophotometric method for the determination of rhodium has been developed.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer fitted with stoppered quartz cells of 10 mm optical path-length. A ECL 5651 digital pH meter was used to measure acidity of the aqueous solution.

Isonitrosothiocamphor was prepared as reported⁴ and a 0.4% solution of the reagent in ethanol was used. All other reagent used were of analytical grade. Stock solution of rhodium(III) was prepared

from RhCl₃.3H₂O (Johnson & Matthey) followed by standardisation⁵. The solution was further diluted as required. Chloroform was distilled before use.

General procedure : To an aliquot of the sample solution containing 50–150 μg of rhodium(III) was added the INTC solution (0.5 ml) followed by addition of a buffer solution (pH 3). The volume of the aqueous phase was maintained at 10 ml. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 10 min, cooled to room temperature and then equilibrated with of chloroform (10 ml) for 1 min. The separated organic layer was dehydrated over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance measured at 345 nm against a reagent blank. Rhodium was determined from a calibration curve. To test the interferences, the respective foreign ions were added to the system before addition of the reagent.

Results and Discussion

The extraction of rhodium complex was investigated in the pH range 0–10. Chloroform extracts showed maximum and steady absorbance when the extractions were carried out at pH 2–4. When the extraction was repeated using the same aqueous phase after a single extraction, the organic extract virtually showed no absorbance. It indicate a quantitative recovery of rhodium in this pH range.

The Rh^{III}–INTC complex in chloroform exhibits absorption maximum at 345 nm with a broad band around 470 nm. The reagent blank shows insignificant absorbance from 340 nm onwards. Wavelength 345 nm was selected for all analytical measurements.

The optimum reagent concentration was ascertained by extracting Rh^{III} at various concentrations of INTC. It was found that 0.5 ml of 0.4% ethanolic solution of INTC was sufficient to extract 50–150 μg of Rh^{III} in a single extraction; higher reagent concentration had no adverse effect, but was avoided because of the higher absorbance of the blank. The mole-ratio method indicated the formation of a 1 : 3 (metal : ligand) complex under the experimental conditions.

The effect of diverse ions on rhodium(III) determination was studied by carrying out the extraction at pH 3.0. Deviation of not more than ±3% from the expected absorbance was taken as the standard tolerance limit for the respective diverse ion. In the estimation of 97.5 μg Rh, the following ions did not interfere when present in amounts (mg shown in parenthesis) : Ca^{II} (8), Ba^{II} (9), Sr^{II} (8.5), Zr^{IV} (7), Th^{IV} (6), Mn^{II} (3), Cd^{II} (4), Zn^{II} (9), Mg^{II} (10), U^{VI} (4), Cr^{III} (2), Al^{III} (10), Pb^{II} (3), As^{III} (8), La^{III} (10). Ni^{II} (2.5) and Co^{II} (0.5) could be tolerated in presence of EDTA. Cu^{II} (2.5) was masked with tartrate. Pd^{II} (0.5) was harmless in presence of ammonium hydrogen fluoride caused less recovery of rhodium. Less than 0.1 mg each of Mo and V could be tolerated. Pt^{IV} was co-extracted with Rh^{III} and thus showed high results. Hg^{II} must be absent. Among the anions, 10 mg each of borate,

phosphate, tartrate, citrate, ascorbate, sulphate and nitrate, 5 mg each of thiosulphate and thiocyanate, and 3 mg each of EDTA, oxalate, fluoride and bromide were tolerated. Presence of iodide showed high results.

The precision and accuracy of the method were tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of Rh^{III} following the recommended procedure. The average of six determinations of 97.5 μg Rh was found to be 97.25 μg with the relative mean deviation of $\pm 1.88\%$.

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Analysis of Thallium(III) and Vanadium(IV) in a Mixture

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Manuscript received 14 March 1988, revised 9 September 1988,
accepted 20 July 1989

THE analysis of Tl^{III} and V^{IV} in a mixture is relevant in the context of the intermetallic compound formation between higher oxidation states of vanadium and thallium¹. A redox method for either ion in a mixture is difficult because of

the availability of more than one oxidation state for both. Again, both V^{IV} and Tl^{III} are individually amenable for complexometric estimation by EDTA but the log K values of their complexes are not separated well enough at 18.8 and 21.5 respectively² and thus a complexometric method for the analysis of the mixture is not directly feasible. However, the present method is feasible for the mixture and makes use of the fact that the oxidant Ce^{IV} is active towards oxidation of V^{IV} but comparatively inert towards Tl^{I} .

Experimental

The method of preparation of solutions, stoichiometry of the reaction and other details were as reported earlier³.

The mixture containing V^{IV} and Tl^{III} in the presence of Tl^{I} and V^{V} was subjected to cerimetric estimation of V^{IV} as done earlier⁴⁻⁶. It is followed by a complexometric titration of the resulting solution with EDTA². The results are shown in Table 1. The thallium(III) alone in exactly the same amount as was taken for preparing the mixture, was also taken separately and titrated complexometrically to provide a check of our analysis.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) indicate that 1×10^{-3} – 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} of Tl^{III} (2 to 40 mg in 10 ml mixture) can be determined. Analysis of less than 5×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} of Tl^{III} is not desirable. Similarly, analysis of quantities greater than 2.5×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} is not feasible due to the formation of a precipitate which obscures the endpoint. The presence of either Tl^{I} or V^{V} , or both, even at the initial stages do not affect the method of analysis. V^{IV} in the range 1.0×10^{-3} – 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} in the mixture is feasible. Table 1 also furnishes results of spectrophotometric analysis of V^{IV} for comparison. It is vital that the redox titration is initially done followed by complexometric titration. The procedure is rapid

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) AND THALLIUM(III) IN MIXTURE

Amount present in mixture (mg)				Amount found by titration (mg) and standard deviation				Amount of V^{IV} found by spectrophotometry (mg) and standard deviation	
Tl^{III}	V^{IV}	Tl^{I}	V^{V}	Tl^{III}	S.D.	V^{IV}	S.D.	V^{IV}	S.D.
39.46	24.28	20.19	17.49	39.78	± 0.08	24.06	± 0.10	24.41	± 0.04
27.40	15.54	20.19	11.20	27.12	± 0.10	15.49	± 0.02	15.46	± 0.06
17.54	15.54	20.19	11.20	17.58	± 0.02	15.49	± 0.03	15.46	± 0.03
9.87	34.97	20.19	6.30	9.76	± 0.10	34.60	± 0.08	34.68	± 0.05
4.98	8.74	11.86	6.30	4.94	± 0.04	8.65	± 0.09	8.76	± 0.01
2.47	3.89	5.05	2.80	2.48	± 0.02	3.86	± 0.05	3.83	± 0.03
1.10	8.74	11.86	6.30	1.09	± 0.03	8.70	± 0.06	8.76	± 0.06